

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE GENUS OF AETHIONEMA R. BR. SPREADING IN FLORA OF NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

Article Brassicaceae Burnett distributed in Nakhchivan flora, belonging to the family Aethionema R.Br. It talks about sexual types. Here, the bioecological characteristics of species - phenophase, life form, ecological group, altitude zone, ecological environment are explained in detail. Aethionema R.Br. It was also mentioned about the subendemic plant of the flora of Azerbaijan, spreading in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic of the genus. The characteristic species of the genus for the Nakhchivan flora of Azerbaijan are reported.

Keywords: cruciferous family, genus, species, subendemic, ecology, phenophase, formation, geographical range.

INTRODUCTION. Brassicaceae Burnett. - species of the cruciferous family is widespread in the world (especially in the Northern Hemisphere). The family includes annuals, biennials, perennials and shrubs. There are decorative, economically important oil-bearing, fruit-bearing, food species of such plants. The family includes both wild and cultivated species. These species are distributed throughout the world and in all ecological environments (mainly in temperature climates) except Antarctica.

OBJECTIVES AND METHODS: Boyahmad area of Julfa district was selected as the research area. The research object is *Aethionema pulchellum* Boiss. & Huet. and other species belonging to the genus *Aethionema* R.Br. of the *Brassicaceae* Burnett family. During expeditions and free itineraries to the area (03 June - 15 July 2022) distribution area and ecological environment of *Aethionema pulchellum* Boiss. & Huet. specie of *Aethionema* R.Br. have been specified. [Qurbanov E.M., Cabbarov M.T.. 2017.; 8, s. 1042-1054; 9, s. 1-66]. Altitude zones and coordinates of the research area have been determined. Researches were carried out in areas with an altitude above sea level (DSH) of 2175 - 2223 m, coordinates - 39° 15' 31" N, 45° 52' 12" E.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS Plants were collected and herbarium in the research area. Species have been identified using various determinants. During the expedition to the territories, *Aethionema* R.Br. The distribution area and ecological environment of the species of the genus have been specified. The species composition of the formation in which the plant is included has been studied.

The *Brassicaceae* Burnett. family has a special placement in the diversity of the flora of the

Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. It is known that there are more than 3 thousand species belonging to 350 genus of the cruciferous family. [Ə.M Talibov T.H., İbrahimov Ə.Ş., İbrahimov, Герман Д. А. 2022]. 165 species collected in 67 genus of the family grow in Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. [Nəbiyeva F., 2013; Talibov T.H., İbrahimov Ə.Ş., İbrahimov Ə.M., 2021].

Aethionema R.Br. (Puljugluot genus) is one of the genus belonging to the cruciferous family. *Aethionema* originates from the ancient Greek words "to clarify, to connect, to thread". In English, it means "stone salt". This name was given to the plant because it grows in stony places.

8 species (5%) of the genus are distributed in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic:

Genus: *Aethionema* R.Br.

Aethionema arabicum (L.) Lipsky

Aethionema cardiophyllum Boiss. & Heldr.

Aethionema cordatum (Desf.) Boiss.

Aethionema diastrophis Bunge

Aethionema edentulum N.Busch

Aethionema fimbriatum Boiss.

Aethionema pulchellum Boiss. & Huet.

Aethionema Szowitsii Boiss. (*A. elengatum* auct.)

Aethionema R.Br. cinsinin *Aethionema cardiophyllum* Boiss. & Heldr., *Aethionema cordatum* (Desf.) Boiss., *Aethionema diastrophis* Bunge, *Aethionema edentulum* N.Busch, *Aethionema fimbriatum* Boiss., *Aethionema pulchellum* Boiss. & Huet. are typical for the Nakhchivan flora of Azerbaijan, *Aethionema edentulum* N.Busch. species is also a subendemic plant of Azerbaijan flora.

Aethionema pulchellum Boiss. & Huet.

Aethionema pulchellum Boiss. & Huet. is one of the plants belonging to the genus *Aethionema* R.Br. *Aethionema pulchellum* Boiss. & Huet. is a multi-stemmed semibush plant with a height of 15-30 cm.

The green leaves are linear and oblong in shape. Green calyx leaves are sometimes dark, pink petals are 6 mm long. It is short columnar. The plant blooms in the 5th month and bears fruit in the 6th month. It is distributed on the dry, stony, rocky slopes of the lower to middle mountain belt. Due to its beautiful leaves and pink flowers, it is very valuable from a decorative point of view.

(Decorative species of the genus *Aethionema* R.Br., Julfa district - Boyahmad village 09. VI. 2022).

Boyahmad village is located 62 km northeast of Julfa district center, on the left bank of Alinja river. During the expedition to the area, the species *Aethionema pulchellum* Boiss. & Huet. was found. The plant is located in Boyahmed village, altitude 2175 - 2223 m. spread at high altitude. The botanical and ecological characteristics of the species belonging to the genus *Aethionema* R.Br. – Pulcugluot are mentioned in the table below:

Table 1

Botanical and ecological characteristics of species of the genus *Aethionema* R.Br.

№	Species	Altitude	Phenophase	Life form	Height belt	Ecological environment
1.	<i>Aethionema arabicum</i> (L.)	5-25cm	V-VI, VI (VII)	Annual grass	Middle mountain belt	Dry, stony, gravelly places and spills
2.	<i>Aethionema cardiophyllum</i> Boiss. & Heldr.	15-25cm	V-VI, VI-VII	semibush	Middle mountain belt	Dry, stony, gravelly places
3.	<i>Aethionema cordatum</i> (Desf.) Boiss.	10-30cm	V-VI, VI-VII	semibush	Middle mountain belt	Dry, gravelly places
4.	<i>Aethionema diastrophis</i> Bunge	15-25cm	V-VI, VII-VIII	semibush	Middle mountain belt	Stony, gravelly places
5.	<i>Aethionema edentulum</i> N.Busch	25-35cm	V, VII-VIII	semibush	Middle mountain belt	Dry, stony, gravelly places
6.	<i>Aethionema fimbriatum</i> Boiss.	25-40cm	VIII	semibush	Middle mountain belt	Rocky places

7.	<i>Aethionema pulchellum</i> Boiss. & Huet.	15-30cm	V, VI	semibush	Middle mountain belt	Rocky, gravelly places
8.	<i>Aethionema Szowitsii</i> Boiss. (<i>A. elengatum</i> auct.)	20-40cm	V-VI, V	semibush	Middle mountain belt	Rocky, mostly calcareous places

As can be seen from the table, *Aethionema* R.Br. The species belonging to the genus are mainly semi-bush due to their life form. Most of these plants are distributed in the middle mountain belt and on dry, stony slopes. The plants of the genus *Aethionema* R.Br are subendemic of the flora of Azerbaijan, and there are species characteristic of the Nakhchivan flora of Azerbaijan. These types and other information are listed in the table below.

Table 2

Subendemic species and other characteristics of the species of the genus *Aethionema* R.Br belonging to the Nakhchivan flora of Azerbaijan

№	Species	Species of Nakhchivan's flora	Subendemic species of Azerbaijan's Flora	Geographic area type	Useful features
1.	<i>Aethionema arabicum</i> (L.) Lipsky			Front Asia	Decorative, fodder
2.	<i>Aethionema cardiophyllum</i> Boiss. & Heldr. -	+		Asia Minor	Decorative, fodder
3.	<i>Aethionema cordatum</i> (Desf.) Boiss.	+		Asia Minor	Decorative
4.	<i>Aethionema diastrophis</i> Bunge	+		Atropatan	
5.	<i>Aethionema edentulum</i> N.Busch	+	+	Atropatan	
6.	<i>Aethionema fimbriatum</i> Boiss.	+		Atropatan	
7.	<i>Aethionema pulchellum</i> Boiss. & Huet.	+		Iran	Decorative, pharmaceutical
8.	<i>Aethionema Szowitsii</i> Boiss. (<i>A. elengatum</i> auct.)			Atropatan	Decorative

CONCLUSION As can be seen from the data in the table, 6 of the 8 species of the *Puljugluot* genus distributed in the flora of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic (75%) are typical for the flora of Nakhchivan of Azerbaijan and one species (*Aethionema edentulum* N.Busch) is a subendemic plant. Half of the species of the genus belong to the geographical area type Atropatan. Also, most of the species belonging to the *Puljugluot* genus (5 species, 62%) are of decorative importance.

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